

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING AUTOMOTIVE TERMS

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ANNOTATION

The scientific goal of the work is to shed light on the lexical-semantic analysis of "Terms that organize the relationship between the passenger and the car and the main mechanisms" in English, to analyze the history of its formation and structural features, and to present a detailed cross-linguistic comparison. In addition, the problems of connection between lexical and conceptual meanings are identified.

Key words: *Term, automotive vocabulary, word formation, automotive industry extra- and intralinguistic situations, multilingual lexemes, mechanical engineering.*

Introduction

Numerous terminological studies conducted on the materials of different languages have consistently revealed in them a unique combination of general linguistic patterns and specific extra- and intralinguistic situations that affect the vocabulary of a particular field of knowledge. The need to study the equivalence of multilingual lexemes and the peculiarities of the formation of special words belonging to the automotive industry arose due to a number of external and internal reasons, among which, in our opinion, the most important are the following. The automotive industry is the largest industry on the global scale of mechanical engineering, and its share is constantly increasing. Every year, up to one billion cars are produced around the world, and this figure is constantly growing. The automobile industry is one of the foundations of economic development in many countries. The level of development of the automobile industry is an indirect indicator of the country's economic well-being.

Methodology

Descriptive method (for the complex description of terminological units), linguistic modeling method (for the construction of the classification scheme and the definition of terminology), onomasiological method (for the purpose of determining the productivity of the methods of word formation), semasiological method, method of quantitative analysis, comparative-historical analysis, method of sopostavitelnogo analysis.

Data collection and Analysis

Along with the increase in the number of manufactured cars, there is also a technological improvement in their design. Currently, the buyer has the opportunity to purchase a hybrid car, which is an intermediate link for the transition to alternative fuels. In the future, hydrocarbon fuels will be used less, which will give way to technologically advanced and environmentally friendly types of energy. In addition, the car of the future is not only a vehicle, but also a concentration of advanced engineering, which gives the owner not only the opportunity to drive, but also replaces some of the actions of the driver himself.

In recent years, our compatriots began to prefer foreign cars. This is clearly shown by the statistics of 2006, according to the results of which more than a million new foreign cars were sold in our country.

Automotive engineering English is a special purpose English based on public college English and automobile related professional knowledge. Especially for the students of automobile service engineering, to learn automotive engineering English well, they must have solid fundamental of Basic English. Automobile engineering English is different from public college English. Vocabularies of public college English, in most cases, will appear polysemy, while in automotive engineering English they are relatively fixed. There are many professional words in automobile professional

English, but there are no rules to follow. Many compound words and derivative words are important characteristics of automotive engineering English. In addition, in the automotive engineering English, especially in the foreign literature or the introduction of automotive technology, the reader may see a large number of abbreviated vocabulary. With the accumulation of professional vocabularies, phrases and other knowledge, the basic elements of automobile engineering English are built, but this is not enough. In the process of language input, only with excellent grammar knowledge can we correctly understand the content of automotive professional English. In the process of language output, students with grammar knowledge can correctly compose words and phrases into sentences, articles, etc. Automotive engineering English is a highly practical course. By the training of professional English reading, translation and writing skills, students can skillfully read the professional English literature, master the basic skills of professional English translation and writing, and lay a solid foundation for relevant work after graduation.

As a complex technological product, the car requires qualified maintenance. It is technically correct but also requires an accessible literature in terms of understanding, much of which has recently been published.

Result and Discussion

Many technological innovations in the automotive industry that appeared in different countries of the world, as a rule, initially have English names. In addition, it should be taken into account that the most motor countries are English-speaking countries, in particular, the United States of America. Thus, we considered it necessary to stop at the American version of English in some aspects of the study.

The main goal of teaching terms related to the automotive industry is to analyze it, which is described as follows:

- conducting an inventory, selecting lexical material in English and Russian within the terminology under consideration for further description, analysis and comparison. Determine the number of terms that most fully describe modern car design and its main parameters;

- to study the history of the emergence, formation and development of the term "Passenger car design and its main parameters" in English and Russian, involving cultural and historical facts;

- identify the factors that influenced the development of this terminology;

- to study the formal and structural characteristics of English and Russian terms and their comparative analysis;

- study of semantic phenomena (ie: synonymy, polysemy, homonymy, antonymy, paronymy and hyponymy) on the term "passenger-car relationship and car structure and its main parameters" in two languages;

- to clarify the interlinguistic compatibility of the main terms of the studied field of knowledge.

Conclusion

The rapid growth of the number of terminological units due to the rapid development of the automotive industry and related industries has led to the emergence of many publications and practical manuals on the studied topics. However, the contradiction of information in this type of literature sometimes causes a number of ambiguities in the understanding of special literature and technical documents. Such problems revealed the need for the regulation and comprehensive unification of terms. However, the effective unification of the terminology system must be based on preliminary linguistic research. In order to create a clear terminological system, it is necessary to determine the laws of natural formation and development of terminology, to distinguish its characteristic features, in this work, a multifaceted study of special units related to historical (diachronic) automobile terminology was carried out.), onomasiological, semasiological, as well as comparative aspect.

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